

EFFECT OF LOADING PARAMETERS ON COMPRESSION DOMINATED FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF IMPACT DAMAGED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Milan Mitrovic, H. Thomas Hahn & Greg P. Carman

*Mechanical & Aerospace Engineering Department,
University of California, Los Angeles, CA 90095-1597, USA*

SUMMARY: In this paper work aimed at characterizing the influence of low-velocity impact damage and loading parameters on fatigue response of AS4/3501-6 quasi-isotropic laminates is presented. Constant amplitude compression-compression fatigue tests indicate that the impact induced delamination does not growth in the absence of local buckling effects and for the load levels below 50% of the CSAI (Compressive Strength After Impact). In the presence of overloads maximum compressive strain that these laminates can sustain without damage growth is reduced substantially, and block loading tests indicate that the high/low sequence is more damaging than the low/high loading sequence. Constant amplitude tension-compression fatigue of impacted laminates shows negligible differences in terms of life and damage propagation modes when compared to the undamaged specimens. Results of this study suggest that clearly defined damage tolerance criteria for impacted composite laminates can be derived from a limited number of tests.

KEYWORDS: impact damage, post-impact fatigue, damage tolerance

INTRODUCTION

In aircraft applications composite panels are routinely subjected to both low-velocity impacts and long term mechanical loading (fatigue). These loading events cause damage to develop in the form of fiber breakage, matrix micro-cracking, and delaminations which lead to material property degradation with the most severe being compression strength. This reduction represents one of the major issues for satisfying the safety requirements of the aircraft structures. Strength reduction of impacted composite panels has been studied extensively over the past decades, and it has been shown that it depends both on the type and extent of damage.

The post-impact fatigue behavior has been studied by a number of researchers on different materials, lay-ups, and for different loading conditions. Stellbrink [1] studied the fatigue behavior under the tension-compression loading of T300/69 and T300/914 quasi-isotropic laminates. From S-N curves, it was concluded that the rate of life reduction is higher for undamaged than for damaged specimens, and that test data agree better with the sudden death model than with the degradation model. Influence of impact damage on fatigue behavior of AS4/3501-6 laminates under tension-tension (T-T), tension-compression (T-C), and compression-compression (C-C) loading was studied by Ramkumar [2]. Fatigue testing was performed at stress levels above 60% of the ultimate strength, and while most of the specimens subjected to T-T loading survived 1 million cycles, all specimens loaded in T-C

and C-C failed well before. The author concluded that tensile loading, static or fatigue, represents the least severe mode to cause additional damage in impacted laminates. In another experimental study by Ramkumar [3], the effect of imbedded (idealized) delaminations on the compression behavior of three different stacking sequence of quasi-isotropic T300/5208 graphite/epoxy laminates was investigated. From the S-N data, it was concluded that the threshold value of the maximum compressive stress, at which failure is not expected to occur, depends on the location and shape of the implanted delamination. Also, the occurrence of delamination growth and its direction is shown to be dependent of the laminate stacking sequence and its through-the-thickness location, and the failures were induced predominantly by the propagation of imbedded delaminations to the tab region. Blaricum et al., [4], studied the compression dominated loading based on the modified FALSTAFF flight by flight sequence on a [+45/-45/0/0]_{7S} XAS-914C impacted specimens. Fatigue testing is performed under the maximum compressive strain of 0.36%, a value close to the design strain used in military aircraft. It is reported that for this type of material and lay-up, the low load levels can be deleted from the testing sequence with no significant effect on fatigue life, and that the duration effect of high-level loads does not influence fatigue life significantly. Some researchers have suggested the fatigue damage tolerance criteria for impacted composite structures that require only static loading [5]. This is based on observations that the impacted composite panels have very flat compression *S-N* curves, and that although compression strength is greatly influenced by the impact damage, any subsequent reduction under fatigue loading is minimal.

While the real service loads are usually kept much lower than the ultimate failure loads, most of the research work on fatigue of composite laminates with impact induced damage has focused on the final failure. The objective of this study is to determine the influence of loading parameters on impact induced delamination growth during fatigue loading, and the fatigue design limits (delamination growth thresholds) for composite laminates containing barely visible low-velocity impact damage. Specifically the effects of load type, load level, load sequence, and the effect of overloads, their magnitude and place in the load spectrum are of interest in this study. Method to accelerate fatigue testing is suggested by extending the results of compression dominated constant amplitude and block loading tests to random fatigue loading.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Quasi-isotropic [0/+45/-45/90]_{S4} laminates made from an AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy material system were used in this study. Gage length of the coupons for static and fatigue tests of 38.1 x 38.1 mm was chosen to prevent the occurrence of buckling effects in the presence of compressive loads. Impact tests are performed on a Dynatup 8200 drop weight impact testing machine with a 6.35 mm and 12.7 mm tup diameters and 4.3 kg impactor weight (cross-head and tup). A modified SACMA SRM 2-88 impact fixture was used to provide the necessary support for the specimens. Modifications were made to accommodate specimens dimensions used in this study, and consisted of a smaller 25.4 x 25.4 mm square cutout instead of the recommended 76.2 x 127 mm cutout. In conjunction with the Dynatup 8200 drop weight impact testing machine, the model 730-I data acquisition and analysis system was used which can provide complete records of impact energy and force as a function of time. Static compression tests are performed on a 50 kN capacity Instron test frame. The specimens were loaded at a displacement rate of 1.27 mm/min, per ASTM D3410-75 standard. An end-loaded compression testing fixture was used, which is similar to NASA

short block compression fixture. The test fixture was placed in the test frame upon a spherical seat which provided alignment of the specimen during compression. Following static tests, the fatigue was performed on a 10 kN capacity Instron test frame. Monitoring damage progression during fatigue loading, via X-ray radiography, was done periodically to assess the change of the damaged area as a function of loading parameters.

IMPACT DAMAGE EVALUATION AND COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AFTER IMPACT (CSAI)

Initial impact tests were performed to determine the influence of impact test parameters on damage development. Impact energies were adjusted to produce barely visible impact damage for subsequent fatigue loading. The overall impact damage area, in the form of a delamination, has been determined via X-ray radiography, and the observed damage size is plotted versus the incident impact energy in Figure 1.a. Caution should be taken when interpreting results for the maximum damage diameter of 25.4 mm achieved in these tests, since it coincides with the 25.4 x 25.4 mm square cutout of the clamping fixture. That is, the damaged area might have been larger if the boundary conditions in these tests were different (i.e., for the larger unsupported area).

Fig. 1. a) Damage area vs. the incident impact energy
 b) CSAI as a function of impact test parameters

As can be seen from Figure 1.a, some specimens that were impacted with the same incident energy of 1.9 Joules, displayed different damage patterns. That is, some specimens contained delaminations 12.7 mm in diameter, while others showed no damage at all. Even sectioning and microscopic examination of these specimens revealed the absence of any damage in the form of matrix cracking or delamination, suggesting that there exists an impact energy threshold below which damage cannot be found (~ 2 J for this material system and lay-up). Above this threshold energy, significant damage occurred, corresponding to 12.7 mm diameter of damaged area and resulting in a damage diameter to specimen width ratio (d/w) of 0.33. Other researchers have also reported the existence of the minimum energy required to cause an impact damage. Choi et al. [6] reported that an impact energy threshold exists for T300/976 graphite epoxy cross-ply composites. The study also showed that stacking sequence

significantly influences the impact energy required to initiate impact damage. Reported values range from 0.52 to 3.1 J, which is similar to the values obtained for our material system. In another study [7] various lay-ups of the carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic toughened epoxy (IM7/977-2) were investigated, including cross-ply and quasi-isotropic. The normalized energy at the onset of incipient damage was found to be on the average 1.5 J/mm (or 9.75 J, if expressed in the total impact energy). These values are much higher than observed in our investigation, which is as expected for 977-2 toughened epoxy system.

Since the objective of this research is to investigate the fatigue growth of barely visible impact damage, an incident impact energy producing a repeatable damage pattern was chosen (2.1 J). A summary of static compression tests of these specimens is presented in Figure 1.b, including all relevant test parameters and associated compressive strengths. As can be seen from the figure, samples that did not contain visible damage showed negligible degradation in the compressive strength with respect to the undamaged specimens. That is, the average CSAI of these specimens (600 MPa) is very close to the value of 621 MPa obtained on undamaged samples. It can be concluded that the compressive strength of impacted specimens is only function of the damage present, agreeing well with the results of Cairns and Lagace [8]. That is, the damage was caused by different impactor mass, velocity and boundary conditions, but for the equivalent damage an equivalent compressive strength is measured. Furthermore, while subjected to slightly different impact energies and different impactors, samples with approximately same delamination of 12.7 mm in diameter experienced very similar compressive strength reduction (Figure 1.b). Average CSAI of these samples is 470 MPa (with a small standard deviation of 18 MPa), which corresponds to 25% reduction when compared to the undamaged specimens. Stellbrink [1] has reported compressive strength reduction of ~50% for impacted T300/69 and T300/914 quasi-isotropic laminates with d/w ratios of 0.32 - 0.44, while Ramkumar [2] investigated the behavior of impacted AS4/3501-6 laminates and observed ~65% reduction in compressive strength. While the ratio of the damaged area with respect to the overall specimen's dimensions in Ramkumar study is almost the same as in current study (i.e., d/w of 0.33), the strength reductions are substantially different. It seems that more accurate qualification of the impact damage, rather than the overall damaged area, is needed in order to compare different test results. Furthermore, compression test method, gage length of the specimen (buckling effects), and definition of the final failure are also parameters which are important in defining the CSAI. The actual 'delamination failure' of the coupons in this study occurs at ~380 MPa, while the final collapse of the specimens occurs much later at ~470 MPa, which is defined as the compressive strength after impact.

POST-IMPACT FATIGUE BEHAVIOR

Summary of fatigue test results including the type of loading, load levels, test frequency and the number of cycles for each specimen is outlined in Table 1. Two specimens were tested per each load level which were chosen between 30 and 70% of CSAI. It should be noted that the variable test frequency (smaller for higher stress levels) was dictated by the limitations of the test frame capacity.

Table 1. Test matrix for constant amplitude and block loading

Specimen #	Test frequency [Hz]	Load level [% of CSAI]	N # of cycles
Constant Amplitude Compression-Compression			
32A6	7.5	40 %	1,000,000
32A7	7.5	40 %	1,000,000
33B1	7.5	50 %	1,000,000
33B4	7.5	50 %	1,000,000
34A8	5	60 %	>500,000
35A5	5	60 %	>400,000
33B2	4	70 %	141,607*
35A6	4	70 %	100,000*

Specimen #	Test frequency [Hz]	Load level [% of CSAI]	N # of cycles
Compression Block Loading (High/Low)			
33B3	4	70 %	100
	10	30 %	1,000,000
33B5	4	70 %	100
	7.5	40 %	1,000,000
Compression Block Loading (Low/High)			
31C7	7.5	40%	1,000,000
	4	70%	>100,000
32A6	7.5	40 %	1,000,000
	4	70 %	45,296*
Constant Amplitude Tension-Compression			
32C5	7.5	30 %	1,000,000
32C6	7.5	30 %	1,000,000
31C5	5	40 %	>600,000
33A6	5	40 %	376,602*
33A5	5	50 %	70,500*
31C4	5	50 %	110,000*

* indicates cycles to final failure

CONSTANT AMPLITUDE (C.A.) COMPRESSION-COMPRESSION (C-C) LOADING

The extent and mode of delamination growth under compression loading varied significantly depending on the applied load level. For specimens cycled at 40 and 50% of CSAI, the impact induced damage did not grow under cyclic loading up to 10⁶ cycles. At higher load levels corresponding to 60% of CSAI only minor growth of impact damage was observed. Moderate delamination growth initiated after 2,000 cycles, and it reached the tab region of the specimen after 50,000 cycles. Schematic representation of this damage pattern, as observed by X-ray radiography, is presented in Figure 2. Growth of this thin delaminated region occurred on the rear impacted side of the specimen, along the lines of impact induced matrix cracks in the outer 0° ply, and is attributed to local buckling of the outer plies. At higher load levels (70% of CSAI) different and more severe type of damage growth was observed, as can be seen from Figure 3. Although there are some variations between specimens, delamination

extended throughout the entire gage section at ~10,000 cycles. This was a consequence of 'delamination failure' which occurred between 100 and 1,000 cycles. Microscopic examination of specimens tested at 70% CSAI indicate more severe damage which spans few outer plies on the rear impacted side of the specimen. However, catastrophic failure of these specimens occurred much later, at more than 100,000 cycles. Again, buckling of the outer plies on the rear impact side was the major factor governing delamination growth at this stress level.

Fig. 2. Growth of impact damage under compression-compression fatigue (60% of CSAI)

Fig. 3. Growth of impact damage under compression-compression fatigue (70% of CSAI)

S-N curves of impacted and previously [9] tested undamaged specimens are presented in Figure 4.a. Stress levels in this figure are normalized with respect to the ultimate compressive strength (UCS) of undamaged specimens, where 100% of CSAI corresponds to 75% of UCS. It is evident that the fatigue life of impacted specimens is reduced when compared to undamaged coupons, especially at higher load levels (> 60% of CSAI or 45% of UCS) where local buckling and damage growth due to delamination failure govern the fatigue response. At lower load levels for which damage did not grow in fatigue, similar performance in terms of life is observed.

Fig. 4. Strength vs. number of cycles (S-N) curve for undamaged and impacted specimens
 a) C-C loading, b) T-C loading. Note: stress levels are normalized with respect to the ultimate compressive strength (UCS) of undamaged specimens

CONSTANT AMPLITUDE (C.A.) TENSION-COMPRESSION (T-C) LOADING

The damage growth under the tension-compression loading resembled the fatigue behavior of undamaged specimens. Specimens cycled at ± 30 of CSAI revealed only ply cracking, and no growth of impact damage up to 10^6 cycles. At higher load levels of ± 40 and ± 50 of CSAI both ply cracking and edge delamination are observed, together with the minor impact damage growth. Schematic representation of the damage pattern at ± 50 of CSAI is presented in Figure 5. While the growth of very thin delaminated region occurs prior to the growth of delamination from the edges, it is the edge delamination that actually governs the fatigue life as in the case of non-impacted specimens. Furthermore, comparison of S-N curves of impacted and previously [9] tested undamaged specimens (Figure 4.b) reveals no differences between the two. Due to the most damaging nature of T-C loading, failure of the laminates occurs at lower load levels than in C-C loading. Therefore, the delamination failure, as observed in constant amplitude C-C loading at 70% of CSAI has no practical importance in T-C loading, and can not influence the damage growth modes for this type of loading. These results suggest that long and costly testing of impacted composite laminates is not necessary for T-C loading as long as the life of non-impacted laminates is known.

Fig. 5. Growth of impact damage under tension-compression fatigue ($\pm 50\%$ of CSAI)

COMPRESSION-COMPRESSION BLOCK LOADING - EFFECT OF OVERLOADS

In order to determine the damage tolerance criteria for impacted composite laminates, constant amplitude tests can provide useful information about the damage growth parameters at different load levels. Based on the results of C.A. tests the fatigue design limit without impact damage growth for this material system and type of initial impact damage corresponds to load levels less than 50% of CSAI (0.5% strain) in the presence of only compressive loads, and $\pm 30\%$ of CSAI (0.32% strain) in tension-compression loading. However, it has been suggested that delamination in composite materials may grow very rapidly for a small load range, and that small uncertainties in the applied load may lead to large uncertainties in delamination growth [10]. This is especially important if the service loads are greater than anticipated. Therefore, the influence of overloads that might occur during the real service conditions on damage growth and fatigue life is investigated next. Since only minor damage growth was observed for specimens tested below 60% of CSAI, emphasis was placed on the sequence of occurrence of high load levels (i.e. 70%).

Two specimens were subjected to low/high block loading to assess the influence of this type of load sequence on damage propagation. After one million cycles at 40% of CSAI (with no visible damage growth) fatigue was continued at 70% until the final failure. Observed delamination growth for these specimens was very similar to the coupons that were tested only at 70% load level. Comparison of normalized delamination area (area of damage / gage section area) for constant amplitude and 40/70 block loading is presented in Figure 6.a. As

can be seen from the figure, for the same number of cycles at 70% the same trend in delamination growth is observed. Also, the number of cycles (at 70%) to final failure of these specimens is comparable to the coupons fatigued at constant amplitude loading (see Table 1). For other fatigue damage modes in composite materials (like ply cracking in tension dominated fatigue) blocked tests have shown that low/high load sequence results in a greater damage [9]. For that case the low loads by itself may not be damaging, but they may aid the subsequent high load to produce greater damage than would otherwise occur without it. For the type of damage in this study the exact opposite behavior is observed.

Fig. 6. Delamination growth as a function of number of cycles
 a) at 70% of CSAI for constant amplitude (70%) and low/high block loading (40/70%)
 b) at 30 and 40% of CSAI for high/low block loading (70/30 and 70/40%)

Fig. 7. Growth of impact damage under block compression-compression loading

Effect of overloads that occur at the beginning of the load spectrum (high/low test sequence) was investigated on two coupons which were initially exposed to 100 cycles at 70%, and subsequently fatigued at lower stress levels (i.e. 30% and 40% of CSAI). Schematic representation of the damage pattern for the second case, as observed by X-ray radiography, is presented in Figure 7. As indicated in this figure, following the overloads that cause 'delamination failure', delamination growth occurs even at these low load levels (for which no growth of impact damage is observed in constant amplitude tests). Normalized delamination area is plotted versus the number of cycles for these two load sequences in Figure 6.b. Examination of these data indicate that delamination growth threshold, for laminates subjected to overloads, is even below 30% of CSAI. Results also suggest that the high/low test sequence for impact damaged composite laminates is more damaging than the low/high sequence.

Based on the results of constant amplitude and block loading some conclusions about the influence of higher load levels on damage progression during random spectrum loading can be inferred. Since high load levels represent less than 0.05% of the total number of cycles in the transport wing spectrum test [11], their magnitude and sequence of occurrence is very important for the appropriate design of standardized certification procedures for impact damaged composite materials. Since a full flight-by-flight spectrum test is long and costly, a method of accelerating this test through truncation of either low or high loads is beneficial [11]. Based on the results of this study, the damage progression modes are expected to be the same for the baseline and truncated load spectrum as long as the highest load levels are kept below the levels that cause 'delamination failure' (i.e., <60% of CSAI). On the other hand, if these high load levels are included in the test spectrum the truncation of either high or low load levels (following a high load level) might lead to unreasonable estimates of fatigue life. However, it should be pointed out that these suggestions apply only for the type of initial damage as used in this study, that is, barely visible low-velocity impact damage.

CONCLUSIONS

Results of impact tests show that a correlation exists between the energy absorbed by the composite during impact and damage induced in it. Furthermore, static compression tests demonstrate that the compressive strength is a function of the damage state only (i.e. absorbed impact energy), and is relatively independent of other impact test parameters. For the laminates impacted close to the impact damage threshold (resulting in a damage-diameter-to-width ratio of 0.33), a 25% reduction in compressive strength was measured. Subsequent constant amplitude compression-compression fatigue tests of these specimens indicate that the delamination does not grow for load levels below 50% of the CSAI. On the other hand, coupons tested at 70% of CSAI and above, exhibited significant delamination growth even after a few cycles. The growth was caused by the delamination failure of the plies located on the rear impact side of specimens. Local buckling of delaminated plies was the reason for delamination growth even when the load levels were reduced to 30% and 40% of CSAI. Furthermore, block loading tests indicate that the high/low sequence is more damaging than the low/high load sequence for compression-compression loading. Fatigue behavior under the constant amplitude tension-compression loading of impacted laminates shows negligible differences in terms of life and damage propagation modes when compared to the undamaged specimens, suggesting that the damage tolerance criteria for this type of loading can be defined from a limited number of tests.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors of this paper gratefully acknowledge the support of the Federal Aviation Administration under grant number 95-G-021. We would also like to thank Peter Shyprykevich and Joseph Soderquist of FAA for their guidance.

REFERENCES

1. Stellbrink, K.K.U., "Influence of Low-Velocity Impact on the Fatigue Behaviour of CFRP Laminates", *Fatigue and Creep of Composite Materials, Third International Symposium on Metallurgy and Material Science*, M. Lilholt and R. Talreja, Eds., 1982, pp. 319-327.
2. Ramkumar, R.L., "Effect of Low-Velocity Impact Damage on the Fatigue Behavior of Graphite/Epoxy Laminates", *Long-Term Behavior of Composites, ASTM STP 813*, T.K. O'Brien, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1983, pp. 116-135.
3. Ramkumar, R.L., "Compression Fatigue Behavior of Composites in the Presence of Delaminations", *Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 775*, K.L. Reifsnider, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1982, pp. 184-210.
4. Blaricum, T.J., D.S. Saunders, G. Clark and T.E. Preuss, "Damage Tolerance of Impact Damaged Carbon Fibre Composite Wing Skin Laminates", *New Materials and Fatigue Resistant Aircraft Design, Symposium*, D.L. Ed., 14th CAF, 1989, pp. 537-556.
5. Demuts, E., R.S. Whitehead, and R.B. Deo, "Assessment of Damage Tolerance in Composites", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 4, 1985, pp. 45-58.
6. Choi, H.Y., H.S. Wang and F.-K. Chang, "Effect of Laminate Configuration and Impactor's Mass on the Initial Impact Damage of Graphite/Epoxy Composite Plates Due to Line-Loading Impact", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 26 (6), (1992), pp. 804-827.
7. Strait, L.H., M.L. Karasek and M.F. Amateau, "Effects of Stacking Sequence on the Impact Resistance of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Toughened Epoxy Laminates", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 26 (12), (1992), pp. 1725-1740.
8. Cairns, D.S. and P.A. Lagace, "Residual Tensile Strength of Graphite/Epoxy and Kevlar/Epoxy Laminates with Impact Damage", *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Ninth Volume)*, ASTM STP 1059, S.P. Garbo, Ed., ASTM, Philadelphia, 1990, pp. 48-63.
9. Hahn, H.T., J. Bartley-Cho, and S.G. Lim, "The Effect of Loading Parameters on Fatigue of Composite Laminates: Part II", *DOT/FAA/AR-95/79 Report*, 1996.
10. O'Brien, T.K., "Towards a Damage Tolerance Philosophy for Composite Materials and Structures", *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Ninth Volume)*, ASTM STP 1059, S.P. Garbo, Ed., ASTM, Philadelphia, 1990, pp. 7-33.
11. Phillips, E. P., "Effect of Truncation of a Predominantly Compression Load Spectrum on the Life of a Notched Graphite/Epoxy Laminate", *Fatigue of Fibrous Composite Materials, ASTM STP 723*, 1981, pp. 197-212.